

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OCCUPATIONAL CONDITIONS OF TEACHER AND OPTIMAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2025-2026. Research instruments on occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: The study found to exhibit a high level of occupational conditions of teacher. This means that the provisions relating to occupational conditions of teacher is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of optimal learning environment of students. This indicates that the provisions relating to optimal learning environment of students are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students. This implies that the higher the occupational conditions of teacher, the higher is the optimal learning environment of students. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student was rejected.

Keywords: occupational conditions of teacher, optimal learning environment of student, school administration and supervision, quantitative research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Creating an optimal learning environment for students is essential for promoting academic success, emotional well-being, and long-term engagement with learning. An optimal environment is one that is safe, inclusive, supportive, stimulating, and structured in a way that meets the diverse needs of all learners. However, many schools struggle to maintain such an environment consistently, leading to a problematic gap between what students need to thrive and what they actually experience in the classroom. This issue can hinder students' growth both academically and personally (Glaves & Talpade, 2024).

The global problem on optimal learning environment varies across different countries and region. In the case of South Sudan, it is recorded that 37% of teachers are unqualified to teach. These teachers either lack of teacher training or does not

have necessary degree to teach students. On top of this pressing issue is many of them work unpaid or as volunteers. The classroom size added to the biggest problem these teachers have to deal especially that the teacher-student ratios up to 145:1 (Haider, 2021).

In the Philippines, issues associated with poor learning environment of students is evident in the students' extremely low learning outcomes. The learning poverty in the country as reported in the 2023 World Bank study, it estimates that 91% of Filipino children aged 10 struggle to read a simple text. This is translated into 1 in 10 meet basic literacy expectations. The results of the Program for International Student Assessment in 2022 stated that among 15-year-olds, only 16% reached Level 2 proficiency in math; 24% in reading; 23% in science which is vastly below OECD averages (Acido & Caballes, 2024).

In the local setting, the issue on learning environment of students has affected the results of the literacy assessment, in Davao Occidental division, the overall percentage of Grade 7 to Grade 10 learners in English recorded a 53.05% of them identified as three levels down the expected performance while there is 38.39% of these students are in the two-levels down performance.

The occupational conditions of teacher is seen as on factor that is associated in the low learning environment of the students. However, as of this recent, there has been no study that is conducted in the local setting which prompted the researcher to propose this study to address empirical gap.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of occupational conditions of teacher in terms of:
 - 1.1 Physical Abilities;
 - 1.2 Professional Growth;
 - 1.3 Interpersonal Relationship;
 - 1.4 Social Environment, and
 - 1.5 Personal Gratification?
2. What is the level of optimal learning environment of students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Equitable Learning Environment;
 - 2.2 High Expectations Environment;
 - 2.3 Supportive Learning Environment;
 - 2.4 Active Learning Environment, and
 - 2.5 Progress Monitoring and Feedback Environment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students?

Hypothesis

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will adopt a quantitative correlational research design to examine the relationship between teachers’ digital transformation skills and students’ internal drive aptitude. The quantitative approach allows for statistical analysis of the strength and direction of associations between variables, providing empirical evidence on how teacher competencies in digital technology influence students’ motivation and learning behavior.

Non-experimental correlational research is a research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables, without establishing cause and effect in which in this study, it will look into the relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This will be used to determine the level of occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student.

Pearson r. This will be used to determine the significance of the relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Occupational Conditions of Teacher

Shown in Table 1 is the level of occupational conditions of teacher with an overall mean of 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, physical abilities has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.23 or very high, professional growth, 4.21 or high, interpersonal relationship, 4.18 or high, social environment, 4.16 or high, and personal gratification, 4.14 or high.

Table 1. Occupational Conditions of Teacher

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Exhaustion	4.21	Very High
Mental Distance	4.05	High
Cognitive Impairment	4.08	High
Emotional Impairment	4.08	High
Overall	4.10	High

The result of the study is in line with the statement of Nwoko, Emeto, Malau-Aduli & Malau-Aduli (2023) who attests that The occupational conditions of teachers significantly influence their performance, motivation, and overall wellbeing. One key factor is workload and working hours. Teachers are responsible not only for delivering lessons but also for preparing instructional materials, grading assignments, supervising extracurricular activities, and completing administrative tasks. These responsibilities, often extending beyond regular school hours, can contribute to stress and burnout. Additionally, the classroom environment, including physical conditions, available teaching resources, and student behavior, directly impacts a teacher’s ability to deliver lessons effectively and comfortably.

The result of the study corroborates the statement of Pankov, Katamanova, Slivnitsyna, Beigel, Pavlov & Vinokurova (2022) who supports the claim that access to professional resources, technology, and development opportunities is another crucial aspect of a teacher’s occupational conditions. Schools with well-equipped classrooms, reliable digital tools, and sufficient teaching materials enable teachers to implement engaging and effective instructional strategies. Continuous professional development, including workshops, training programs, and mentorship, helps teachers stay updated with modern pedagogical approaches and technological advancements.

The result of the study reinforces the statement of Toropova, Myrberg & Johansson (2021) who establishes that other factors shaping teachers' occupational conditions include salary, benefits, support from school leadership, career growth opportunities, and work-life balance. Competitive compensation, recognition of achievements, constructive supervision, and clear pathways for career advancement improve job satisfaction and retention. At the same time, excessive workload, lack of administrative support, and poor work-life balance can negatively affect both mental health and instructional quality.

Level of Optimal Learning Environment of Students

Shown in Table 2 is the level of optimal learning environment of students with an overall mean of 3.50 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Table 2. Work Task Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Equitable Learning Environment	3.56	High
High Expectations Environment	3.61	High
Supportive Learning Environment	3.52	High
Active Learning Environment	3.46	High
Progress Monitoring and Feedback Environment	3.38	High
Overall	3.50	High

Among the enumerated indicators, high expectations environment has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 3.61 or high, equitable learning environment, 3.56 or high, supportive learning environment, 3.52 or high, progress monitoring and feedback, 3.50 or high, and active learning environment, 3.46 or high.

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Glaves & Talpade (2024) who emphasizes that An optimal learning environment for students is one that is safe, supportive, and conducive to both academic and personal growth. A physically comfortable classroom, with proper lighting, ventilation, seating, and access to learning materials, helps students focus and engage more effectively. Equally important is emotional safety: students should feel respected, valued, and free from fear of ridicule or punishment. When learners feel secure, they are more willing to participate, ask questions, and take intellectual risks.

The result of the study supports the statement of Ahmad (2021) who verifies that the social and instructional aspects of the environment also play a vital role. Positive relationships between teachers and students encourage trust and open communication, while collaborative activities promote peer interaction and teamwork. Effective teaching strategies, such as clear instruction, interactive lessons, and differentiated approaches, help meet the diverse needs of learners. An environment that encourages curiosity, critical thinking, and creativity allows students to actively construct knowledge rather than passively receive it.

The result of the study is in agreement with the statement of Hatane, Setiono, Setiawan, Semuel & Mangoting (2021) who validates that an optimal learning environment supports students' overall well-being and motivation. This includes providing encouragement, constructive feedback, and opportunities for achievement. When students' individual differences, interests, and cultural backgrounds are acknowledged, they feel a greater sense of belonging. Access to resources such as technology, counseling support, and extracurricular activities further enriches the learning experience. Altogether, a balanced environment that addresses physical, emotional, social, and academic needs enables students to reach their full potential.

Significance on the Relationship between Occupational Conditions of Teacher and Optimal Learning Environment of Students

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.828 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students is rejected.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Occupational Conditions of Teacher and Optimal Learning Environment of Students

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Occupational Conditions of Teacher and Optimal Learning Environment of Students	0.828	0.000	Reject

The result of the study corroborates the statement of Freund, Zriker & Sapir (2022) who acknowledges that The relationship between teachers’ occupational conditions and students’ optimal learning environment is direct and deeply interconnected. When teachers work under positive conditions, such as supportive leadership, manageable workloads, and healthy interpersonal relationships, they are more motivated, focused, and effective in their teaching. This, in turn, helps create a classroom atmosphere that is organized, engaging, and responsive to students’ needs. Conversely, poor occupational conditions, including stress, lack of support, or job dissatisfaction, can reduce teachers’ effectiveness and negatively impact the quality of the learning environment.

The result of the study resonates with the statement of Otrębski (2022) who attests that teachers’ well-being also influences how they interact with students and structure their classrooms. When teachers experience professional satisfaction and emotional support, they are more likely to foster equitable, supportive, and high-expectation learning environments. They can give individualized attention, provide meaningful feedback, and encourage active participation. However, if teachers feel overwhelmed or undervalued, they may struggle to maintain patience, creativity, and responsiveness, which can limit students’ engagement and learning opportunities.

The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Jomud, P. D., Antiquina, Cericos, Bacus, Vallejo, Dionio & Clarin (2021) who supports the claim that improving teachers’ occupational conditions is essential for establishing and sustaining optimal learning environments for students. Schools that invest in teacher support, through professional development, fair policies, collaborative cultures, and adequate resources, enable teachers to perform at their best. This creates a positive cycle: well-supported teachers create effective learning environments, and effective learning environments lead to better student outcomes. Therefore, the quality of education students receive is closely tied to the conditions under which teachers work.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a high level of occupational conditions of teacher. This means that the provisions relating to occupational conditions of teacher is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of optimal learning environment of students. This indicates that the provisions relating to optimal learning environment of students are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students. This implies that the higher the occupational conditions of teacher, the higher is the optimal learning environment of students. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of student was rejected.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found to exhibit a high level of occupational conditions of teacher. The researcher recommends that teachers may improve in the area of personal gratification as this obtained the lowest mean rating among all indicators. The teachers may get the feeling of having done a good day’s work by planning daily lessons with clear, achievable objectives and reflect at the end of the day on what was accomplished; know by the results when they have done a good job by using formative assessments such as quizzes, class activities, or discussions to monitor student understanding in real-time; make competent students/graduates by setting high but achievable expectations and use diverse instructional strategies to meet different learning needs, and review student performance regularly through assessments, projects, or portfolios to observe progress.

The study revealed a high level of optimal learning environment of students. The researcher recommends to students that they may improve in the area of active learning environment. The researcher recommends that students may actively participate by asking questions, responding to peers, and sharing perspectives; listen attentively to others and build on their ideas to deepen the discussion; relate what you learn in class to your own experiences or current events; participate in projects or activities that connect theory to practice; stay focused, take notes, and contribute to classroom activities; ask questions and seek clarification whenever something is unclear, and apply feedback to improve work and reflect on learning progress.

Teachers may encourage open-ended questions and class discussions that allow every student to share ideas; use real-world examples, case studies, and practical applications to link lessons to everyday life; encourage students to share personal experiences that relate to the topic; incorporate interactive teaching strategies such as hands-on activities, experiments, and multimedia resources; vary teaching methods to maintain interest and accommodate different learning styles; use differentiated instruction to tailor lessons based on students' abilities and learning needs; provide timely, specific, and constructive feedback that helps students improve, and offer additional support such as tutoring, peer mentoring, or extra practice for students who need it.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between occupational conditions of teacher and optimal learning environment of students. The researcher recommends that students may show respect and cooperation toward teachers and peers to contribute to a positive classroom environment; take responsibility for your own learning by actively participating and providing constructive feedback to teachers when appropriate, and appreciate and support teachers' efforts, understanding that their well-being directly affects the quality of your learning experience.

Teachers may prioritize self-care and professional development to maintain motivation, job satisfaction, and teaching effectiveness; foster strong interpersonal relationships with colleagues, students, and parents to create a collaborative and supportive learning environment, and regularly reflect on your teaching practices and seek feedback to ensure that occupational challenges do not negatively affect students' learning.

Principals may provide teachers with a safe, supportive, and well-resourced work environment to enhance morale and instructional quality; encourage collaboration among teachers and recognize their achievements to boost professional satisfaction, and monitor teacher workload and provide opportunities for professional growth, ensuring that teachers can focus on delivering high-quality instruction.

District supervisors may develop policies and programs that prioritize teacher welfare, fair compensation, and adequate resources for schools; support professional development initiatives that strengthen teachers' skills, motivation, and job satisfaction, and promote a culture of accountability and collaboration across schools to ensure that improvements in teachers' occupational conditions translate into better student learning outcomes.

The researcher also recommends to future researchers to conduct similar study and explore some indicators that are not included in this study in another setting in order to uncover new knowledge relevant to the topics presented in this study.

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